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EU-PolarNet 2 - Co-ordinating and Co-designing the
European Polar Research Area

Deliverable No. D5.2

EU-PolarNet 2 communication package

Submission of Deliverable

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SUMMARY

The EU-PolarNet2 communication package includes presentation and poster templates and logos for project partners, along material for project dissemination (folder draft, factsheet draft). In addition, ideas for “give aways” are listed. An overview of the project webpage (www.eu-polarnet.eu) and the social media channels (Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn) is included.

1 Introduction

Communication is key to connect science with society. To reach as many as possible, all available channels of communication are used, spanning from the traditional printed materials like the folder over to social media such as Instagram. A uniform design is used in all included materials to foster the recognition of the project.

2 Main Objectives

The main objectives of the communication package are 1) to provide project partners with standardized templates and logos to use in project related communication, and 2) to summarize all means of project dissemination, online (webpage and social media channels) and in print format (factsheet, folder). Ideas for give aways are listed.

2.1 Materials for project partners

Via the projects' internal dropbox and website, partners can access templates for presentations and posters and the mandatory logos (EU flag, Horizon2020, EU-PolarNet). All templates follow a uniform design in order to foster project recognition.

2.2 Project dissemination

2.2.1 Webpage

The new webpage is hosted by wordpress. The address stays the same than in EU-PolarNet 1 (www.eu-polarnet.eu).

Screenshot of new EU-PolarNet 2 webpage, www.eu-polarnet.eu

2.2.2 *Social media*

Facebook: The face book page of EU-PolarNet has currently 1764 members (14.12.2020).

Twitter: Currently 2091 followers (14.12.2020).

Instagram: Currently 101 subscribers (14.12.2020).

LinkedIn: Currently 87 members (14.12.2020)

2.2.3 Fact sheet

The factsheet is a 2-page pdf document providing a general overview about the project (i.e. numbers, funding, partners, work packages, ...). It is intended to provide clear and condensed information in a format that can easily be shared online.

www.eu-polarnet.eu

At a glance

Title:	Coordinating and co-designing the European Research Area
Instrument:	Coordination and Support Action
EU contribution:	€3,299,253.75
Duration:	4 years (01.10.2020–30.09.2024)
Project Coordinator:	Biebow, Nicole
Coordinating Organisation:	Alfred Wegener Institute Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research (AWI)
Project Website:	www.eu-polarnet.eu

The Challenge

The Polar Regions are sentinels of climate change and human resilience and they are also a proven bastion for international cooperation in research and nature protection. European-funded researchers have made significant contributions to understanding the consequences of climate change and the structure and functioning of ecosystems at both Polar Regions, and their global interconnections. Unifying, disseminating and coordinating of all European research actions plays a key role in achieving and demonstrating the EU's contribution to the generation of knowledge with relevance for society, economy, environment and policymaking.

The Objectives

EU-PolarNet 2 will provide a platform to co-develop strategies to advance the European Polar research action and its contribution to the policy-making processes. Once EU-PolarNet 2 ends, the gained experience, the established network and the tools developed to facilitate better coordination and co-design of Polar research actions will be transferred to and sustained by the European Polar Coordination Office (EPCO).

Consortium

ALFRED-WEGENER-INSTITUT HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM FÜR POLAR-UND MEERESFORSCHUNG	DE	WORLD OCEAN COUNCIL EUROPE	FR
MINISTERIO DE CIENCIA, INNOVACION Y UNIVERSIDADES	ES	SERVICE PUBLIC FÉDÉRAL DE PROGRAMMATION POLITIQUE SCIENTIFIQUE (BELSPO)	BE
OULUN YLIOPISTO	FI	ARCTIC MONITORING AND ASSESSMENT PROGRAMME SECRETARIAT	NO
CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	IT	INSTITUTO DE GEOGRAFIA E ORDENAMENTO DO TERRITORIO DA UNIVERSIDADE DELISBOA	PT
NORGES FORSKNINGSRAD	NO	POLARFORSKNINGSSEKRETARIETET	SE
EUROPEAN POLAR BOARD	NL	UNITED KINGDOM RESEARCH AND INNOVATION	UK
NEDERLANDSE ORGANISATIE VOOR WETENSCHAPPELIJK ONDERZOEK	NL	ISTANBUL TEKNİK UNIVERSİTESİ	TR
STYRELSEN FOR FORSKNING OG UDDANNELSE	DK	Jihočeská univerzita v Českých Budějovicích	CZ
CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	FR	RANNSOKNAMIDSTOD ISLANDS	IS
UNI WERSYTET SLASKI	PL	HAVSTOVAN	FO
BULGARSKI ANTARKTICHESKI INSTITUT ASSOCIATION	BG	INTERNASJONALT REINDRIFTSSENTER	NO
UNIVERSITÄT WIEN	AT	ECOLE POLYTECHNIQUE FEDERALE DE LAUSANNE	CH
TALLINNA TEHNIKAÜLIKOOL	EE		

Thematic Activities / Work Packages

Work Package 1: Research Coordination

EU-PolarNet 2 will strengthen the European Polar Research Area by establishing tools and services to sustain a durable intra-European and international cooperation in Polar Research. EU-PolarNet 2 will coordinate the EU Polar Cluster, a growing network of EU-funded Arctic and Antarctic research projects and as such a pre-existing example for improved cooperation.

Work Package 2: Stakeholder Involvement

EU-PolarNet 2 will develop procedures to ensure that all relevant stake- and right holders are involved in the prioritisation of Polar research needs and will co-design Polar research actions. It will collect best practises, create processes and provide strategies for capacity building and continued meaningful stake- and right holder involvement and make these publicly available in an online repository

Work Package 3: Research Prioritisation

EU-PolarNet 2 will develop strategies to advance European Polar research in an international dimension through stakeholder involvement and co-designing of future research plans. It will further identify and develop globally significant large-scale Polar research initiatives.

Work Package 4: Research Optimisation

EU-PolarNet 2 will provide an overview and better understanding of the landscape of Polar research funding in Europe and of the diversity and coordination potential of European Polar research programmes. It will stimulate better alignment of the Polar research funding programmes by bringing national operators and funders of Polar research closer together.

Work Package 5: Policy Advice, Dissemination, Communication

EU-PolarNet 2 will provide evidence-based advice in response to questions related to the Polar Regions from the EC and to other decision makers at national and regional levels. Its Policy Advisory Board (PAB), a representative group of European experts on Polar issues, will guarantee rapid response and evidence-based advice on pressing Polar scientific and socio-economic issues.

Work Package 6: European Polar Coordination Office (EPCO)

EU-PolarNet 2 will accelerate the development of a fully integrated Polar observing system, characterised by sustained monitoring and the provision of priority observation services, by facilitating better coordination of the European Polar observing community and its capacities. WP6 will also perform the preparatory work for the implementation of the European Polar Coordination Office as a legacy of EU-PolarNet 2.

The Impact

1. Support of the creation of a European Polar Research Area and a substantially advanced Polar research cooperation in Europe.
2. Contribution to improved coordination of national resources and investments in European Polar research to ensure their more synergetic use.
3. Improved policy advice at regional, national and EU level and support of the EU's international commitments with respect to Polar sciences.
4. Improved cooperation of international Polar research programmes to create the basis for the development of future large-scale joint international Polar initiatives.
5. European-wide agreed and prioritised Polar research actions.

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2.2.4 Folder/brochure

The brochure is a print document intended to be shared at conferences and other meetings. Like the fact sheet it provides brief and condensed information.

Our Goals

- Advance European and International polar research coordination across all disciplines
- Provide strategies for meaningful stake- and right holder involvement
- Support the development of transdisciplinary and transnational Polar research actions
- Interact with national funding agencies to develop synergies and optimise the use of resources
- Provide evidence-based policy advice to decision makers
- Support the implementation of sustained observation systems in the Arctic and Antarctic
- Create a permanent European Polar Coordination Office (EPCO)

Image: Justina Dahl

www.eu-polarnet.eu

Consortium

The EU-PolarNet 2 consortium consists of 25 partners representing all European and associated countries with Polar research programmes and activities. This enables EU-PolarNet 2 to significantly improve the coordination and co-design of European Polar research actions but also to provide evidence-based advice for policy-making processes on behalf of the whole European Polar community.

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Eu-PolarNet 2 Programme Office

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www.eu-polarnet.eu

Co-ordinating and Co-designing the European Polar Research Area

www.eu-polarnet.eu

Anticipated impact

- Advanced Polar research cooperation across Europe, support for the creation of a European Polar Research Area
- Improved cooperation of international Polar research programmes fostering future large-scale joint international Polar initiatives
- Increased synergetic use in European Polar research by coordination of national resources and investments
- Improved policy advice at regional, national and EU level and support of the EU's international commitments with respect to Polar sciences.
- Europe-wide agreed and prioritised Polar research actions

EU-PolarNet

EU-PolarNet 2 is a coordination platform for co-developing strategies for European Polar Research and its contribution to policy-making.

www.eu-polarnet.eu

Our ambition

- To establish a sustainable and inclusive coordination platform to co-develop and advance European Polar research actions
- To support policy-making processes by providing evidence-based advice
- To sustain the coordination platform in a permanent European Polar Coordination Office (EPCO)

2.2.5 Give aways

Should be convenient and sustainable. First ideas are Drinking bottles (e.g. from Bamboo or recycled materials), Notebooks from recycled paper, USB-sticks.

3 Outlook

All online communication channels are continuously updated with recent news from the network.

4 Annexes

4.1 Screenshot Facebook

4.2 Screenshot Twitter

EU-PolarNet
950 Tweets

EU-PolarNet
@EUPolarNet

EU-PolarNet - Coordinating and co-designing the European Research Area. Funded by @EU_H2020. Tweets reflect only the views of the project owner.

📍 Bremerhaven, Germany 🔗 eu-polarnet.eu 📅 Joined April 2015

784 Following **2,091** Followers

[Edit profile](#)

4.3 Screenshot Instagram

4.4 Link to LinkedIn Group

<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/6971671/>